

and a 10–15% yield loss in the transplanted aman season nationwide.

The 1998 transplanted aman crop was severely affected by a long-lasting flood, which reduced the rice-cropped area significantly. Widespread outbreaks of rice gall midge, *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason), and sheath blight, caused by *Rhizoctonia solani*, occurred in the early planted higher lands. When the flood peak subsided, farmers transplanted rice in medium-high lands. In some areas, severe outbreaks of rice leaffolders [*Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* (Guenée), *Marasmia patnalis* (Bradley), and *M. exigua* (Butler)] occurred on late-planted rice fields. A high incidence of BPH and swarming caterpillar, *Spodoptera mauritia* (Boisduval), was also observed in many areas. The 1998 transplanted aman crop suffered 20–25% yield losses from flood and pest outbreaks.

In response to the shortfall in transplanted aman rice production in 1998 and the anticipated increase in rice market price, farmers expanded the boro area in

the following season. Historical data indicated that, after severe floods and loss of transplanted aman rice, farmers met the shortfall by increasing boro rice coverage in the following season (see table).

Recent abnormal weather patterns have perhaps contributed to the unusual outbreaks of BPH, gall midge, leaffolders, and sheath blight in Bangladesh. For insect pests in 1998, ovipositing females may have aggregated in higher elevation rice fields when low-lying fields were flooded. Later generations of adults may have migrated to young rice plants in late-planted fields.

Two other trends might have contributed to the disease and insect problems: the higher use of nitrogenous fertilizers and misuse of insecticides. A positive correlation between levels of N application and sheath blight incidence is often observed because higher N levels result in increased canopy density. It is well established that insecticide misuse can cause outbreaks of some pests, such as BPH, because of the disruption in naturally occurring biological control agents.

BIRRI will continue to monitor trends in weather patterns and pest outbreaks. If pest outbreaks persist, it may be necessary to change research and rice-breeding priorities in Bangladesh.

Farmer participatory research for rat management in Cambodia

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In 1998, CIAP researchers worked with a local nongovernment organization (CRS) to begin a program of farmer participatory research (FPR) for improved rat management in Svay Teap District of Svay Rieng Province in southeastern Cambodia. The research was compatible with the action research process used by CRS as a way of empowering local farmers to find

Effect of abnormal high floods on boro (winter) rice coverage and production in Bangladesh.^a

Year	Flood situation in previous monsoon	Boro rice area planted to modern varieties		Modern variety boro rice production	
		(ha × 10 ³)	Change over previous year (%)	(t × 10 ⁶)	Change over previous year (%)
1973-74	Normal flood	589	—	1.6	—
1974-75	High flood	659	11.9 ^b	1.6	1.2
1975-76	Normal flood	642	-2.6	1.6	0
1976-77	Normal flood	492	-23.4	1.2	-27.0
1977-78	Normal flood	589	19.71	1.5	25.2
1978-79	Normal flood	600	1.9	1.4	-7.4
1979-80	Late flood	724	20.7	1.9	36.2
1980-81	Normal flood	747	3.2	2.0	5.8
1981-82	Normal flood	898	20.2	2.5	26.1
1982-83	Normal flood	1,081	20.4	3.0	20.7
1983-84	Normal flood	1,006	-6.9	2.8	-6.6
1984-85	High flood	1,230	22.3	3.4	18.7
1985-86	Normal flood	1,213	-1.4	3.2	-3.9
1986-87	Normal flood	1,340	10.5	3.6	11.8
1987-88	High flood	1,639	22.3	4.3	19.8
1988-89	Very high flood	2,132	30.1	5.4	26.3
1989-90	Normal flood	2,154	1.0	5.7	4.6
1990-91	Normal flood	2,266	5.2	6.0	4.9
1991-92	Normal flood	2,334	3.0	6.4	7.1
1992-93	Normal flood	2,351	0.7	6.2	-2.0
1993-94	Normal flood	2,335	-0.7	6.4	2.9
1994-95	Normal flood	2,410	2.3	6.2	-3.4
1995-96	Normal flood	2,507	4.0	6.8	10.4
1996-97	Normal flood	2,547	1.6	7.1	3.9
1997-98	Normal flood	2,670	4.5	7.8	9.8
1998-99	Very high and long-lasting flood	3,500 ^c	31.1	10.0 ^c	27.9

^aData compiled from *Statistical yearbook of Bangladesh* (published annually), Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics, Dhaka. ^bEarly phase of modern variety boro adoption. ^cTentative estimate.

solutions to their own problems. They had already identified rat control as a key issue in the management of rainfed lowland rice crops. In Cambodia, these crops are usually transplanted. The objective was to identify weaknesses in farmers' rat management practices and to work through possible improvements with them.

Farmers reported two to five kinds of rats attacking their crops. Their descriptions coincided with accepted rodent taxonomy. Collections of rats made by hunting and trapping confirmed the presence of three species in, or near, rice fields: *Rattus argentiventer*, *Bandicota indica*, and *Rattus exulans*. Farmers were convinced that rat populations are local, living in bunds around rice fields and in nearby wooded areas. They did not consider mass migration of rat populations to be important in Svay Teap.

Researchers considered rat management to be a community issue because rats move around the landscape so easily and over long distances (individual landholdings are often 1 ha or

less): what one farmer does, or does not do, to manage rats affects other farmers in the community. Farmers and researchers met to discuss the rat problem, how farmers control rats now, and what opportunities exist to do something about it. Researchers took part in a community rat hunt organized by villagers (both in the daytime and at night). Night hunting was less effective than hunting and digging burrows during the day. In three villages, we provided the materials to build a plastic fence with traps around an early wet-season (EWS) rice crop to make an active trap barrier system (TBS). Some EWS and dry-season rice farmers in Cambodia already use a plastic rat fence to protect their crop. Farmers' existing experiments with EWS rice provided an opportunity to test the TBS technology. They built and maintained the TBS and monitored the traps. Researchers trained farmers in improved baiting, burrow digging, and rat damage assessment in rice crops. Farmers maintained records of the number of rats captured by different methods, which were

used to estimate the effectiveness of different technologies. A visit by a rodent ecologist from the Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organization (CSIRO) in Australia provided additional insights into the rat species present and the management implications of behavioral differences between rat species.

Traps and baits were already widely used, but these did not give adequate control. Farmers proposed rat hunts as a possible remedy. The TBS was not used in wet-season rice crops in Svay Teap because it is too expensive, although farmers did agree to help test this technology if we paid for it. Except for hunting/digging, all the technologies have limitations (see table). We believed that we could improve the effectiveness of baiting and trapping by paying attention to the quality of materials and through training in techniques. But we saw little we could do to improve the effectiveness of the TBS—the major problem is the high cost compared with the losses associated with rat damage. A

Comparison of technologies used in farmer participatory research in Svay Teap District, Svay Rieng Province, Cambodia.

	Baiting	Traps	Hunts/digging	TBS ^a
Initial cost	Medium	Medium	Low	High
Labor requirements	Low	Low	Medium	High
Effectiveness	Low	Medium	High	Low
Durability	Days	Years	NA ^b	A season
Reliability	No	Yes	Yes	No
Economies of scale	No	No	Possible impact of community rat management	Yes (cost t ⁻¹ depends on field size and shape)
Provides information about rat populations	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Requires continuous monitoring	No	Yes	No	Yes
Environmental hazard	Yes	No	No	Unknown
Gender impact	Primarily men's work	Primarily men's work	Men, women, and children	Men and women
Health impact	Unknown	No	Positive	No
Compatibility with farming system	No (livestock)	Yes	Yes	No (livestock)
Complexity	Medium	Low	Low	High
Adaptability	Farmers modified bait stations using aluminum cans	Novel trap designs were well accepted	Adapted to include dogs in the hunt	Difficult to modify, but possible use as fish fences
Relative disadvantage	Some rat species are bait-shy; presence of cattle reduces effectiveness of baiting	Traps do not target rats that attack rice crops; theft	May require community organization	High cost; high complexity; need for continuous monitoring; incompatible with cattle in the farming system; theft
Popularity	Individuals	Individuals	Basis for social interaction	Initial interest, but this dissipated

^aTBS = trap barrier system. ^bNA = not applicable.

rat hunt in the dry season appears to be a viable alternative that is comparatively well accepted, uses easily available resources, avoids problems of theft and effects on cattle, and can be targeted to small rat populations close to rice fields at the end of the dry season.

Recent discussions of sustainability (e.g., Cox et al 1997, Röling and Wagemakers 1998, van Veldhuizen et al 1997) have emphasized the importance of participatory learning as a way of coming to grips with the complex issues of environmental management. Our experience with FPR in Svay Teap has already provided significant gains in terms of

- An improved basis for the choice of technology, e.g., dismissal of the TBS

option for wet-season rice crops in areas like Svay Teap where yields are low, and rejection of using the EWS crop as a trap crop because its timing does not coincide with high rat populations.

- Identification of immediate opportunities to improve practices, e.g., baiting and trapping.
- Modification of solutions proposed by farmers as technology is progressively adapted to the local farming system, e.g., the use of beer cans as bait stations. These are more durable than coconut shells, and there is less chance of poisoning cattle.
- Identification of an improved strategy for rat management (digging for rats

in bunds in the dry season, possibly as a community activity).

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Digital Literacy for Rice Scientists

To help rice scientists take advantage of new information and communication technologies, the IRRI Training Center has developed the *Digital Literacy Course for Rice Scientists*. The course aims to provide scientists with information about what resources are available on the Internet and how they can go about accessing these resources.

The course is unique in that, it focuses on the needs of rice scientists, it provides a forum for rice scientists to share their experiences and Internet resources with other rice scientists online, and it establishes a learner-centered knowledge network in the form of an online community centered on rice research.

The topics covered by the course include

- What is the Internet
- What is the World Wide Web and what makes it work
- Key Internet terminology
- How to use the Internet for communication with other scientists
- How to use Web browsers
- How to search for information efficiently and effectively
- What are some of the good sources of information for rice scientists available on the Internet
- How to cite Internet documents
- What training opportunities are available online

Connection to the Internet offers national scientists with a low-cost communication medium with other scientists linked to the Internet, gives them access to the ever-growing body of information available on and through interlinked computers throughout the world, and provides access to formal and informal training offered online from virtually anywhere.

The course was developed by Robert T. Raab and Buenafe Abdon of the IRRI Training Center. Watch for more announcements in subsequent issues of IRRN.

